

Figure 4: Current Self-Determination Theory Regarding Motivation



Gagné, Marylène, and Edward L. Deci. 2005. "Self-Determination Theory and Work Motivation." *Journal of Organizational Behavior* 26 (4): 331362. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.322>.

Adapted from (Gagné and Deci 2005, 336)